

GEOSPATIAL MODELLING OF URBAN GREEN SPACES IN AWKA, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

Urban green space (UGS) plays an important role in the ecosystem, such as reducing the amount of carbon in the atmosphere, providing shade and habitat for animals, improving air quality, lowering air temperatures, retaining and filtering stormwater, sequestering carbon, and making cities look better and feel healthier. This study assessed the changes in the urban green spaces across the metropolitan area of Awka, Anambra State, Nigeria, using remotely sensed data. The pattern of changes in the UGSs over 30 years using a ten-year interval from 1993-2023 was examined by analyzing from LANDSAT datasets using supervised classification into five (5) land cover classes, namely; vegetation, grass/ agricultural land, waterbody, built-up area, and open space. Data of each class were subjected to descriptive statistics. The result revealed that Awka metropolis has witnessed rapid urbanization in recent decades leading to a dramatic decline in vegetation (from 4.7% in 1993 to 1.1% by 2023). This research also reveals a shift in urban morphology with built-up areas expanding from 7.9% to 29.6%. This study concluded that the amount of vegetated area and open spaces within Awka Metropolis diminishes with an increase in built-up area. Hence, massive tree planting is recommended for areas with less vegetation.

Key words: *Anambra, GIS, Land cover, Land Use, Urban Forestry, Remote Sensing*

INTRODUCTION

Urban green spaces are geographical areas made up of trees, forests, gardens, agricultural land, waterways, and other natural areas as well as outdoor green spaces. Urban Green Space (UGS) is thought to improve urban dwellers' health and wellness (Wim *et al*, 2021). They primarily appear in cities as controlled parks and gardens, which are semi-natural environments, with sporadic pockets of vegetation connected to roadways and other incidental spots. Being a fundamental component of urban regions, green spaces are essential to the preservation of biodiversity and the provision of essential ecosystem

services. It is now understood that trees—both in parks and on streets—are essential to urban forests and ecosystems, serving as more than just aesthetic elements. Urban trees improve air quality, lower air temperatures, retain and filter stormwater, sequester carbon, and make cities look better and feel healthier; These are only a few of the socioeconomic and environmental advantages of urban trees (McPherson and Simpson, 2003; Nowak *et al.*, 2006). According to Nowak and Dwyer (2007), the advantages and applications span from air pollution reduction and urban climate improvement to intangible psychological and artistic benefits. Avenue trees and urban woodlands benefit society in many ways, both environmentally and socially.

The distribution of green area accessibility and distance across Awka City are closely related to meeting recreational needs (Chukwu *et al.*, 2022). Since 1993, Awka City has experienced development, growth, and construction activities such as building, road construction, deforestation, and many other anthropogenic activities that have resulted in the loss of biodiversity, degradation of water catchments, and increase in greenhouse gasses that have far-reaching effects. Green spaces were transformed into urban areas as a result of Awka's quick growth (Okoye and Ngwu, 2021). According to UN-Habitat (2012), 62% of the population of Anambra State living in the urban centers, hence, the state is one of the mostly built-up states in Nigeria (Okoye and Ngwu, 2021). Ezeomedo and Igbokwe (2019) and Igbokwe *et al.* (2019), highlighted that urbanization is rapidly expanding across the entire state and is projected to accelerate in the near future.

Geographic information system based spatial statistics have enabled the development of accurate, logical explanatory urban green space variables, including sight, accessibility, density, size, and connectivity. Features of the Earth's surface, particularly the qualities of vegetation, can be captured by remote sensing. This led to modifications in the land cover, with expected rising urban populations, and independent extreme heat events are predicted to increase and become compounded, with the greatest impact being seen in urban areas (Liao *et al.*, 2021). Urban green spaces are our natural mitigation tool that absorbs sunlight for photosynthesis, protects humans from incoming radiation, and releases cooling moisture into the air. Unfortunately, urban areas typically have low levels of vegetation which leads to increased land surface temperature. The increased energy consumption during extreme heat leads to elevated emissions of air pollutants and greenhouse gases, which contribute to more ground-level ozone (Kennedy *et al.*, 2009). Therefore, the study aimed to assess changes in urban green spaces in the Awka metropolis of Anambra State, Nigeria for sustainable urban tree and environmental management.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Area

This study was carried out in Awka Metropolis, the capital of Anambra State, Nigeria consists of two Local Government Areas; Awka North and Awka South which lies

between latitudes 6°06'N and 6°16'N and longitudes 7°01'E and 7°10'E (Figure 1). The temperature in Awka is generally 27-30°C between June and December but rises to 32-34°C between January and April with the last few months of the dry season marked by the intense heat. It has an average annual temperature of 26.3°C. It has a rainfall pattern ranging from 1828-2002 mm. The climate of Awka falls within the tropic wet and dry type based on Koppen’s classification (Chukwu *et al.*, 2020).

Figure 1. Map of Awka Metropolis

Data Collection

The data used for this study was remotely retrieved from the United States Geological Survey Agency (USGS) through their Earth Explorer web portal (<https://glovis.usgs.gov/>). Satellite imageries (LANDSAT) for the years 1993, 2003, 2013, and 2023 were downloaded for the study area based on availability. The image characteristics are shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Data used in this study

Landsat type	Path and row	Years	Bands	Date(capture)
Landsat5 TM	188/056	1993	2,3,4	1993/01/17
Landsat7 ETM ⁺	188/056	2003; 2013	2,3,4,	2003/01/08; 2013/01/17

Landsat8 OLI 188/056 2023 3,4,5 2023/01/07

Landsat 5 TM – Thematic mapper, Landsat 7 ETM⁺- Enhanced Thematic mapper, Landsat 8 OLI – Operational land Imager. Resolution= 30 × 30 m, average cloud cover= 5%

Data Analysis

Satellite imagery of Awka was collected for the years 1993, 2003, 2013, and 2023, followed by a series of processing steps. These steps included image composition, rectification, enhancement, and classification. The classification process was essential for complementing visual analysis with quantitative techniques, allowing for the identification of features within the study area with more focus on green and non-green spaces.

To determine the identity of green spaces and their rates of change, a supervised maximum likelihood classification method was applied to Landsat 5 TM, Landsat 7 EMT+, and Landsat 8 OLI/TIRS satellite imageries. This process successfully categorized the landscape into five (5) classes (vegetation, grass/ agricultural land, waterbody, built-up area, and open space). A descriptive analysis was then performed to present the change detection results alongside relevant statistical data regarding these transformations. Classification of the land cover of each year was analyzed using spatial statistics, as follows:

$$Area = count \times 0.09 \tag{1}$$

$$Cover\ changes = End\ Year - Initial\ Year \tag{2}$$

$$Rate\ of\ change\ (km^2/year) = \frac{End\ Year - Initial\ Year}{interval\ in\ years} \tag{3}$$

Land cover data was further analysed using percentages and bar charts.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The percentage change of the land cover classes in the research years and the estimated areas of all the land cover classes— Vegetation, Grass/Agricultural land, Waterbody, Built-up area, and Open space —are also shown in Table 2, the percentage of vegetation in 1993 was 4.7%, it increased to 52.3% in 2003; decreased to 16.3% in 2013, and further decreases to 1.1% in 2023. This is most likely due to the removal of trees for development. This is in agreement with Olisa *et al.* (2023) who found a similar pattern in Akure metropolis, Nigeria (Table 2). Built-up areas on the other hand had a regular increase in 1993 (7.9%), 2003 (20.6%), 2013 (23.9%) and 2023 (29.6%) as presented in Table 2 and Figure 2. This implied that more areas were converted to buildings. This was higher than the highest (21.77%) reported by Alo and Nwatu (2018) for the built-up area in Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria. This is also confirming the low diversity assertion by Chukwu *et al.* (2022) for avenue trees Awka metropolise of Anambra State, Nigeria.

Table 2: Awka metropolis Urban Green Space area and percentage table

Class name	1993		2003		2013		2023	
	(km ²)	%						
Vegetation	8.01	4.7	89.3	52.3	27.9	16.3	1.9	1.1
Grass/Agric. land	89.87	52.6	38.3	22.4	98.4	57.6	115.5	67.7
Waterbody	0.17	0.2	0.2	0.1	0.3	0.3	0.2	0.1
Built-up area	13.44	7.9	35.1	20.6	40.7	23.9	50.5	29.6
Open space	59.12	34.6	7.9	4.6	3.6	2.1	2.7	1.6

Figure 2: Urban Green Space of Awka metropolis from 1993-2023

The changes in Awka metropolis were observed between three periods, from 1993-2003, 2003-2013 and 2013- 2023. Figures 3, and maps for change detection Figure 4. The highest change occurred under vegetation from the year 1993 to 2023, there was a gain of about 81 km² followed by a loss in vegetation from 2003 to 2013 (Figures 3 and 4). The

result also showed a continuous increase in built-up areas and a decrease in open spaces over the years under investigation. This follows a similar trend as reported for Ibadan (Alo and Nwatu, 2018), Jos (Rikko *et al.*, 2022), and Akure (Olisa *et al.*, 2023) metropolises in Nigeria. This is in agreement with the reports of Ezeomodo and Igbokwe (2019) and Igbokwe *et al.* (2019), that urbanization is rapidly expanding across the entire state, especially Awka metropolis.

Figure 3 Green space and non-green spaces in Awka between 1993 and 2023.

(C) 2023-2013
Figure 4. Change detection of Awka from 1993 and 2023.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

The study's findings indicated that the Awka metropolis has seen a rise in urban areas and a decline in vegetated areas. Additionally, the amount of vegetated area and open spaces diminishes with an increase in built-up area. Hence this research recommends massive urban tree planting and sustainable urban planning.

REFERENCES

- Alo, A.A. and Nwatu, J. U. (2018). Modeling urban green space dynamics and associated proximate drivers in Ibadan Metropolis, Ibadan, Nigeria. *Forests and Forest Products Journal*, 18:24-32
- Chukwu, O., Ezenwenyi J. U. and Kenechukwu, T. V. (2020). Checklist and abundance of open grown medico-ethnoforest tree species in Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka, Nigeria. *Asian Journal of Biological Sciences*, 13: 105-112. <https://doi.org/10.3923/ajbs.2020.105.112>.
- Chukwu, O., Umeh, C. L., Ozomma, L. C., Maduabuchukwu, C. K. (2022). Assessment of species diversity, crown and stem diameter distribution of avenue trees in Awka, Nigeria. *Journal of Forest Science and Environment*, 7: 20 – 26.
- Ezeomodo, I. C. and Igbokwe J. I. (2019). Mapping of urban features of Nnewi Metropolis using high resolution satellite image and support vector machine classifier. *Journal of Environment and Earth Science*, 9 (6): 116-130
- Igbokwe, E. C. Emengini, E. J. and Ojiako, J. C. (2019). Evaluation of development dynamics of Awka capital territory, Anambra state, using remote sensing. *International Journal of Engineering and Computer Science*, 9 (4):21719-21728
- Kennedy, E.H., T.M. Beckley, B.L. McFarlane, and S. Nadeau (2009). Rural-Urban Differences in Environmental Concern in Canada.

- Liao, J., and Chen, Q. (2021). Biodegradable plastics in the air and soil environment: Low degradation rate and high microplastics formation. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhazmat.2021.126329>.
- McPherson, E. G., and Simpson, J. R. (2003). Potential energy savings in the building by an urban tree planting programme in California. <https://doi.org/10.1078/1618-8667-00025>
- Nowak, D. J. and Dwyer, J. F. (2007). Understanding the Benefits and Costs of Urban Forest Ecosystems. In: Kuser, J.E. (eds) *Urban and Community Forestry in the Northeast*. Springer, Dordrecht. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4020-4289-8_2
- Nowak, D. J., Crane, D. E., and Stevens, J. C. (2006). Air pollution removal by urban trees and shrubs in the United States. *Urban Forestry and Urban Greening*, 4(3–4): 115-123. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ufug.2006.01.007>
- Okoye, P. U. and Ngwu, C. (2021). Assessing the adequacy and sustainability performance of multi-family residential buildings in Anambra State, Nigeria. *Regional Sustainability*, 2(1): 23-35. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.regsus.2021.01.003>
- Olisa, C. L., Oyinloye, M. A., Olajuyigbe, A. E., Akande, S. O. and Olisa, B. S. (2023). Changing Patterns of Urban Green Spaces in Akure, Nigeria, *International Journal of Environmental Engineering and Development*, 1(1): 157-174 <https://doi.org/10.37394/232033.2023.1.18>
- Rikko, L. S., Pwajok, N. R, Namo, J. A. and Habila, S. K. (2022). Depletion of Urban Green Spaces in Jos Metropolis, Nigeria. *Sahel Journal of Geography, Environment and Development*, 3(2): 67-77.
- Un-Habitat (2012). Nigeria: Onitsha urban profile. United Nations Human Settlements Programme, Nairobi, Kenya.

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